

Experiential learning through students non-profit organizations: ESTIEM case study

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Abstract

European Students of Industrial Engineering and Management (ESTIEM) is a non-profit organization of Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) students that was founded in 1990 to support common activities and relations across Europe. Through it, students engage in activities that promote a combination of technological understanding with management skills. Belonging to this type of organization during their graduation time, gives students a plethora of competences that are learned beyond the classes, outside the university walls. These competences are acquired through experiential learning. The objective of this paper is to present ESTIEM creation, evolution and organization. Also, projects participation, events organization and meetings organized are presented as outcomes of ESTIEM students' engagement. This paper intends also to explore how the participation on this type of organization allows students to develop competences and contribute to the IEM student's education. Following the key competencies for lifelong learning recommended by the Council of European Union, some examples of key competences acquired from the experience of the authors are given. Results showed that being member of ESTIEM allows them to develop such competences and they felt better prepared for the labour market.

Keywords: Engineering education, experiential learning, Industrial Engineering and Management, non-profit organizations.

1 Introduction

Experiential learning is founded in many authors contributions from different sources (Kolb, 1984), namely, Dewey ideas of democratic education (Dewey, 1938), action research theory (Lewin, 1946) and Piaget (1973). Both are based on the learning from experience or "learning by doing" concept that advocates learning resulting naturally from doing. By doing, students learn because it demands engagement in significant situations where he/she generates, supports, and clinches ideas, perceiving the meanings and make connections. Experiential learning is an instructional approach in which students learn through direct experience (either spontaneous or designed and organized by the teacher) and reflection (McComas, 2014). Thus, experiential education first immerses learners in an experience and then encourages reflection about the experience to develop new skills, new attitudes, or new ways of thinking (Lewis & Williams, 1994). Itin (1999) adds that in experiential education, carefully chosen experiences supported by reflection, critical analysis, and synthesis, are structured to require the learner to take initiative, make decisions, and be accountable for the results, through actively posing questions, investigating, experimenting, being curious, solving problems, assuming responsibility, being creative, constructing meaning, and integrating previously developed knowledge. Most of the time, the students are autonomous and independent to learn by their own terms and rhythm.

These situations could be promoted in academia by active learning methodologies (Felder & Brent, 2006; Prince, 2004) and/or promoted by non-formal education environments such as student non-profit organizations or unions. In these students' unions, students develop a range of functions for their members such as organization of events; social and training activities; support of academic and welfare issues; students representation on local and national issues, among others (Brooks et al., 2015).

This is the kind of activities that Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) students, members of European Students of Industrial Engineering and Management (ESTIEM), develop by being members of this organization. This paper is about this participation and how these students learn in this non-formal context through experiential and independent learning.

By developing such type of activities, students acquire key competencies related to the development of essential interpersonal, communicative and cognitive skills (ability and capacity to carry out processes and use the existing knowledge to achieve results) such as: critical thinking, analytical skills, creativity, problem solving and resilience (Council of the European Union, 2018). These skills are embed in the key competences that are listed by Council of the European Union (2018) as: 1) Literacy; 2) Multilingual; 3) Mathematical, science, technology and engineering; 4) Digital; 5) Personal, social and learning to learn; 6) Citizenship; 7) Entrepreneurship and; 8) Cultural awareness and expression (2018, p. 15). Beyond the skills, competencies implies knowledge (facts and figures, concepts, ideas and theories which are already established and support the understanding of a certain area or subject) and attitudes (disposition and mind-sets to act or react to ideas, persons or situations) (Council of the European Union, 2018; Rychen & Salganik, 2000). These facilitate the transition to adulthood, active citizenship and working life, establishing better cooperation between different learning settings and promoting a variety of learning approaches and contexts(Council of the European Union, 2018).

This paper is organized in five sections. After this first introduction, a brief theoretical background approaching the students' union contribution to independent learning and competencies development will be presented. The third section gives an overview of the ESTIEM creation and evolution and main projects, events and training sessions organized by ESTIEM. The fourth section presents the ESTIEM activities contribution to the key life-long learning competencies, as recommended by the Council of the European Union (Council of the European Union, 2018), development in ESTIEM members. Last section draw some final considerations.

2 Students' unions contribution to independent learning and competencies development

Independent learning, or similar terms such as autonomous learning, self-directed learning, student-centred learning, self-regulated learning, self-instruction has been defended and promoted as an important educational goal (Bolhuis & Voeten, 2001; Leathwood, 2006; Meyer, 2010), helping to promote autonomous, and thus lifelong learners (Lau, 2017). Grounded in the literature, Hockings et al. (2018) describe independent learning as:

- Taking responsibility for one's own learning;
- Choosing and setting one's own objectives;
- Deciding what, as well as, when and how to learn;
- Monitoring one's own progress;
- Developing an ability for inquiry and critical evaluation;
- Evaluating and reflecting on what has been learnt;
- Within the context of programme of study, facilitated by an academic.

According to Broad (2006) independent learning aims to teach students to learn for themselves and in turn empower them in their learning whatever the context. No matter the individual definition, the overall consensus appears to be responsibility or ownership of learning on the part of the learner (Mckendry & Boyd, 2012). According to Meyer (2010) the models of independent learning build on the theoretical notion of learning styles such as experiential learning of Kolb (1984). Kolb (1984) proposes a learning model formed by four related stages, where learning starts from a "concrete experience", that passing through a phase of "observation and reflexive processing" allow to assimilate a new set of "abstract concepts and generalizations". This together with an "active experimentation" allow to apply what each one have learned for future experiences.

Independent learning can be promoted through formal curricula in a teacher-student relationship (Itin, 1999; Meyer, 2010; Hockings et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the shift of responsibility for the learning process from the

teacher to the student can also be achieved through students autonomous learning (Itin, 1999; Thomas, Jones, & Ottoway, 2015), namely, through the participation in students unions.

Astin (1999) defines a students' organization as an organization run by college students where student growth and development influenced by peer-groups. Vieira (2019) adds that student unions are a group of students enrolled in higher education who come together with the goal of developing activities that enrich the academic experience of the college in which they operate. Moreover, Holzweiss et al. (2007) emphasize that through students unions students can get personal benefits directed towards their goals, such as gains in field knowledge, providing them the opportunity to learn and broaden their awareness of their specific academic discipline or interest (Fakharzadeh & Todd, 2010). Participation in student unions can also be a useful indicator of leadership training, communication skills, and personal qualities (Fakharzadeh & Todd, 2010), and research suggests that social networks made through clubs and societies can help graduates find jobs and progress in their careers (Andrewartha & Harvey, 2017).

Since always that the main students' involvement in higher education has been related to their work in forming higher education communities through student representation (Ashwin & McVitty, 2015). Student unions are responsible for representing the interests of students, communicating student views to university management, and providing extra-curricular opportunities through clubs and societies, thus representing students and advocating for their rights and interests (Andrewartha & Harvey, 2017).

Students' unions have a long history and tradition in Higher Education. In Portugal, the oldest students' union dates back 1887 and was established at University of Coimbra (Fernandes, Cunha, Torres, 2020). Nowadays, in every Higher Education Institution (HEI) several broad and specific students' unions coexist. Despite that fact, the role of students' unions seems to have remained largely unexplored within academic research (Brooks et al., 2015).

More and more, besides representing students and advocating their rights and interests, students unions are helping to ensure that students receive the best possible experience during their time in higher education, provide several services in the interest of students (Brooks et al., 2015; Guan et al., 2016), develop projects in institutions, identify experienced student representatives for project work or carry out reviews of learning processes at the institutional or faculty level (Attard et al., 2010). In this way students are exposed to several experiences that promote independent learning.

In a recent study, through a survey research, Vieira (2019) concluded that the set of competences that students most develop during their involvement in students organizations are those related to the ability to work in different teams, to communicate with others and also to the leadership capacity, being developed mainly through activities such as the organization of events, participation in multidisciplinary teams and team management. Furthermore, the same author could also conclude that student organizations are felt as an alternative means for the development of skills required by the labour market.

In another recent study, Haines (2019) adds that students consider that being involved with student organizations allow them to apply what they learn academically to "real-world" settings and allow them to develop skills that prepare them for future success. Furthermore, for the students that were involved in her study, where focus group interview was used as research instrument, student organizations serve as a gateway to developing one's leadership skills because holding a leadership role within a student organization provide them opportunities for acquiring, developing, and practicing specific skills. All the referred skills are embed in the key competencies lifelong learning recommended by (Council of the European Union, 2018), referred in the introduction section.

3 ESTIEM context and organization

This section briefly presents the ESTIEM origins, context and organization, highlighting the most important events since the creation to the current projects and events.

3.1 Creation and evolution

European Students of Industrial Engineering and Management (ESTIEM), started in 1990, with its first Council Meeting being in Berlin, where the first statues were signed by the 14 Universities at the time. The first big project of ESTIEM internationally was the big travel that was organized to Japan in 1993, where many ESTIEMers went to Japan to discover new trends in Total Quality Management and made a report out of it to present to their friends once back to Europe. Besides, many other initiatives were developed, like the first edition of the official ESTIEM Magazine (1991) and the appearance of the flagship Case Study Competition Europeanly in 1994, Tournament in Management and Engineering Skills (TIMES) a competition that remains, until today, as one of the biggest in any NGO Europeanly.

On a more intermediate stage of its history, ESTIEM started in 2005 to have its first Summer Academic Events, something that opened ESTIEM to the sector of personal development of its students, where in the time-span of 2 weeks, students were guided by a professor in a topic of self-reflection and self-leadership to define long-term goals for their lives. Thus, following, ESTIEM started to have, in 2009 and 2010, Braintrainer and Academic Days, respectively, being the first project focused in soft-skills and the latter in research and hard-skills knowledge that the Universities could offer the best. Also, during these times, in 2009, ESTIEM started its ESTIEM Student Guide Project, a project that consisted of creating a massive compilation of knowledge about the curriculum and Universities of ESTIEM and put it displayed on the ESTIEM portal.

As for bigger external relations and in the field of Education as well, ESTIEM started its journey in 2010, with the establishment of the position of Vice-President of Education. Since then, ESTIEM had many great opportunities at a large scale that shows its own development. Here, ESTIEM developed, for three straight years, from 2015-2017, EMTA (European Master Thesis Award), a European Competition of Master Thesis that students of IEM could apply for. Moreover, ESTIEM developed great relationships with many partners like *Société Européenne pour la Formation des Ingénieurs* (SEFI), PREFER Project, European Institute of Industrial Leadership (EIL) and European Professor of Industrial Engineering and Management (EPIEM), that allowed it to develop research tools that are now allowing ESTIEM to become a great platform for professionals to get valuable information on the Industrial Engineering and Management field (IEM). On an event based performance, ESTIEM developed in 2016 and 2017 the IEM Education Forum, an event that had the purpose of getting together professors, students and companies to improve the current state of the curricula of IEM in Europe and the Industry proximity to the IEM curricula. ESTIEM in 2018, also started partnering with Inchange, a Dutch company that develops an education simulator about Supply Chain and, thus, ESTIEM uses it for a competition on Supply Chain Management. In Figure 1 a summary of the association history is presented.

Figure 1: ESTIEM history milestones

Regarding the European Management of the Association, ESTIEM develops its functions through two main structures: Central ESTIEM Teams and Local Groups, being thus a confederation of associations under a big umbrella, the European one. In Europe, ESTIEM is officially represented by six Board Members, accountable for everything that happens both centrally and locally in ESTIEM. As for the control of the regions in ESTIEM, there are eight Regional Coordinators, people that support and develop the Local Groups organization. As for the

events and innovation processes Europeanly in ESTIEM, the Board sends every three months Open Calls for the Local Groups to organize events and every month an Open Call for Local Members to join the European Teams and be part of the Committees and Departments.

Thus, every Local Group has opportunities to perform events made available by the Central Teams and also to develop their own people Europeanly. All of this event coordination is monitored by the Vice-President of Activities and all the Educational Projects where Local Groups can have an impact are coordinated by the Vice-President of Education. ESTIEM arrived here nowadays after a great effort of its Members Committee during its history, a Committee in ESTIEM focused in acquiring new Local Groups and as well as in maintaining them sustainable and happy, through the Local Group Support System, an internal team of consultants ready to help when in need. ESTIEM started with 14 Universities, having today 75+. Figure 2 presents the map with the local groups.

Figure 2: Localization of Local Groups (<https://estiem.org/localgroups>)

3.2 Projects, events and partners

As for the projects and events that are developed, ESTIEM is divided in four main departments: Academic, Career, Intercultural and Personal.

Not focusing completely on the last two, just to mention they encompass a great percentage of ESTIEM's portfolio and through them, ESTIEM delivers language courses and Self-Leadership and Reflection Camps, through the services "Language Programme" and "Summer Academy", respectively. These are two areas of ESTIEM that allow IEM Students to personally develop and improve their intercultural awareness and thus developing a more united Europe.

On the first two, instead, is where ESTIEM creates more external value and delivers as well the necessary complementary hard-skills for students in Europe. In Career Department, ESTIEM holds its landmark of competitions: Tournament in Management and Engineering Skills (TIMES), a case study competition hold since 1994 and that shows the best team of IEM Students in Europe in solving case studies, being it the biggest competition in this category in any possible NGO in Europe. Furthermore, Career Department also develops entrepreneurship events, a Business Booster, that allow, later on, if the participants want, to incubate their ideas in partner Startup Incubators of ESTIEM. As for the Academic Department, this is the one that holds the more hard-skills related events and offers a great variety of events to raise students voice and be able to exchange valuable opinions with professionals in the area of Education.

As examples, ESTIEM offers, in this department, a Green Belt Certification in the field of Quality Management, with scientific revision of the content being done by professor Gregory Watson, being this the service ESTIEM has as best value proposition. As a follow-up, ESTIEMers can apply their knowledge on companies and develop a project and get a Green Belt Certificate. Alongside this, ESTIEM also develops a Worldwide Competition on Supply Chain Management, sponsored and supported by a Dutch company, called Inchange, that allows students to simulate the operations of a Supply Chain and take strategic decisions in groups. Lastly, in this department, ESTIEM also has the IEM Summit, an event that has the purpose of gathering students, professors and companies together to improve an aspect of our educational systems, such as the Curricula of IEM in the Universities.

So, in conclusion of the last paragraph, most of the opportunities of the Career and Academic Department offer students great critical thinking and core knowledge on IEM matters, relevant for their future as professionals. Besides, many students, through these opportunities, also develop relevant networking contacts that prove to be relevant for getting their first jobs internationally, as many students get in contact with multiple companies in these experiences. Regarding the quantity of offer of the events in ESTIEM, it has usually more than 180 events per year (Figure 3).

Figure 3: ESTIEM web site main page (<https://estiem.org/>)

Finally, it is worth to mention the Council Meetings and the IEM Conference. The Council Meetings happen twice a year, with around 250 active members of ESTIEM, where the 75 Local Groups gather to take democratic decisions and benchmark between each other to improve themselves. This is usually considered the biggest and most important event for the network improvement. On the other hand, for external and professional purposes, ESTIEM also develops the IEM Conference. The IEM Conference it is a one week event that aims to gather Universities, Companies and Students around IEM topics, to not only discuss them, but as well as to make progress on those, such as Data Science and Supply Chain Management. These events allow students to develop their public speaking techniques, often required in front of big crowds and as well as their adaptation skills, as many times insecure questions arise in these events.

Currently, ESTIEM make partnerships with 18 organization, among them there companies that support the projects and events, universities and others non-profit organizations (Figure 4).

Figure 4: ESTIEM partners (<https://estiem.org/partners>)

4 ESTIEM contribution to IEM students' education during their graduation

Attending to the key life-long learning competencies defined in the introduction, the authors provide some examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes of each competency implicitly or explicitly acquired by the students by organizing, performing and/or being involved in the activities of ESTIEM. Table 1 presents such examples.

Table 1: Competencies developed by ESTIEM students

Competencies	Knowledge	Skills	Attitudes
Literacy	Process and framework of writing a scientific paper	Ability to design a scientific research process	Interest in writing or analysing scientific papers; interest in developing scientifically and educationally IEM
Multilingual	English language	Language development; proficient use of the English language	Initiative to speak to everyone inside the network and work in teams in English language; initiative to join events where new languages are taught by the members of the LGs
Mathematical, science, technology and engineering	Lean Six Sigma; Supply Chain Management, curriculum and career analysis	Problem-solving, critical thinking; data collection, treatment and visualisation and reporting of the information concluded	Initiative to make informed decisions and to understand and influence the European IEM context
Digital	Be aware of new tools to communicate and work	Digital tools use (e.g. elium, tableau, google drive and forms, skype, slack, whatsapp, ...)	Initiative to use different tools, to share, process and store information
Personal, social and learning to learn	Plan a project and activities, distribute individual and team tasks, establish contacts with a company; Public presentation, facilitation	Negotiate and solve conflicts, Initiative to present a topic and answer to questions, development of interpersonal relationships	Initiative to take an active role inside a project or team; initiative to better communicate and interact in public
Citizenship	Actions on how to impact the Sustainable Development Goals	Development of social environmental campaigns	Initiative to plan, execute and participate in social impact activities
Entrepreneurship	Manage projects and collaborate in multidisciplinary team; Applied management theoretical knowledge	Mobilize resources; usage of strategic frameworks (e.g. SWOT, Porter's 5 forces, Root Cause Analysis, etc)	Stimulus and motivation to make the project, initiative to perform strategic analysis on problems and situations
Cultural awareness and expression	Context of cultures in a political, educational and economic scenario	Intercultural awareness	Culture exchange, sensibility for the cultural differences

In ESTIEM, IEM Students end up acquiring many skills that Universities' Educational System can't provide at first sight. As for a first easy division of thoughts, ESTIEM delivers a vast majority of soft-skills that the Universities can't deliver, something that makes the services ESTIEM offer attractive products at the very end for students.

As for the variety of soft-skills ESTIEM delivers, some deserve highlighting, as the following: intercultural awareness – ESTIEM is a great ecosystem that enables students to get to know other cultures in a deeper perspective, not only by getting to know their traditions on social and personal life, but also by integrating international teams that work remotely on various topics of the organization; team management and leadership – ESTIEM offers a unique opportunity to lead teams and work on an international setup, something Universities do not offer on a daily basis. Moreover, once in the Board of an association, students develop skills similar to top managers of international multinational firms, something that stands out right away in a CV selection/filtering process; last but not least, analytical thinking – it's been one of the trends of the past years that ESTIEM is becoming a data-centric organization, where many of its processes are being monitored both in dashboard and in process maps, allowing the top management layers to take decisions based on perceived trends. This allows students to apply data analytics skills in an organization environment, something Universities can't offer at such scale and not even with similar real use cases.

On another perspective, ESTIEM offers as well, as other NGOs do so, great skills of facilitation, Training and Working Session Delivery and brainstorming. These skills need to be highlighted as in ESTIEM, these are developed in a structured and hands-on approach, by applying certified theories that make its members a great addition to companies when student enter the labour market, proving to be efficient employees in situations of presentations and meetings within their own teams or with external partners.

On a final note, the involvement in these International associations has to be pondered upon what each student wants out of his/her professional life. It is 100% recommended for students seeking an international environment in their lives, as well as for the ones looking for jobs that demand a high pace of business meetings. Regardless, it is an experience every student recalls as one of their best in their student life.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents ESTIEM students' union as an experiential and independent learning provider of competencies to their members. ESTIEM is a non-profit organization whose members are IEM students from all Europe. Being a member of such organization bring many advantages to the students that acquire important competencies that prepare them to work in a global and multi-cultural environment. Such informal learning could provide technical and transversal competencies, nevertheless the transversal ones are the most practised such as learning a different language. There are a lot of skills embed in the key competencies referred that could not be learned in lectures, as good as they could be prepared, such as culture exchange, be aware of social and political issues of different countries, citizenship involvement, among others. As a future work, it is proposed to develop a survey that inquiries ESTIEM members about the competencies they think that they acquire with this membership.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020 and UIDB/04058/2020.

6 References

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